

**RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN LONELINESS AND MENTAL DEPRESSION
AMONG COLLEGE STUDENTS**

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Abstract

The present study relationship between loneliness & Mental Depression among college students. Loneliness and mental depression is an important factor for mood when people feel lonely that time he suffer depressed mood that time people do the suicide attempt . A sample of 80 college student located Pune hadpasar District, age range 20to 21 years. Loneliness Inventory constructed and developed by Uma, Meenakshi under the guidance of Krishnan measure Loneliness. Mental Depression measure mental depression this test constructed dubey. Research design t test and correlation analysis. Result relevant that significant of relation between loneliness & mental depression and other hypothesis gender difference loneliness & mental depression of college student.

Introduction:

Today's life very complicated many people facing has differential problem. In current area college students has facing many problem for. Ex. Social, educational, economical, and psychological. In this regard loneliness and mental depression taken into consideration in the present study.

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Loneliness

Loneliness is defined as the sad yearning for understanding that results from perceived deficiencies in the number and quality of friendship social and emotional two types of loneliness. The intensity of social loneliness is related to the degree of discrepancy between one's desired number of friends and one's actual number of friends. How much emotional loneliness one feels is resolute by the difference between one's required level of relationship and one's actual level of relationship. Loneliness can sometimes be a steppingstone to depression, which is a more serious emotional disorder. Well-known

signs of depression include feeling tired & damaged out, sensation inundated by aggressive with everyday life, sensation unable to cope, experiencing opinion about insignificance or not playing a helpful role in life having require of attention in otherwise enjoyable actions feeling gloomy and navy and having so little power that even the easiest task seems too complicated.

Loneliness is a sign in which needs are not being satisfied. Alienation from one's social group is another. isolation is the painful sensation of wanting more person speak to or relationship than you have. The stereotype of the alone person is a communally inept loser who doesn't know how to get beside with others who possibly envying other people . Who have associates and lovers, but latest study has begun to shade a very dissimilar image there are very little differences between alone and not alone persons Thus alone does not mean alone.

Loneliness is a subjective construct related to the concepts of social isolation, alienation, social connectedness, lack of belonging and social capital. there are three types of loneliness 1) Situational loneliness 2) Formative Loneliness 3) Internal Loneliness.

Mental Depression

The term depression covers a variety of negative moods and behavior changes. Some are normal mood fluctuations and others meet the definition of clinical problems. The mood change may be temporary or long -lasting. It may range from a relatively minor feeling of melancholy to a deeply negative view of the world and an inability to function effectively. Symptoms of depression are also likely to occur in bipolar disorder. For this reason the term unipolar disorder is often used when discussing different types of depressive disorder, to distinguish between people who have experienced one or more episodes of depression but no manic or hypo manic episode and those who have a past history that includes at least one episode of mania or hypomania. Individuals who have one or more episodes of mania or hypomania as well as periods of depression are diagnosed as having bipolar disorder.

One study followed a group of depressed individual for many years and found that 78 % were having difficulties at 25 year follow up and on average, had three major depression during the 25 year period in another study 49.1 % of young adults who recovered from a major depression developed another sever. Depression within 18 month having another DSM diagnosis (Such

as anxiety) in addition to depression and the occurrence of interpersonal difficulties were good predictors of recurring depression. Depression can be described as a state of aversion & low mood that can have an effect to the latest who figures over 300 million people are suffering from depression.

There are several studies in which mental depression and loneliness. Achterbergh, L., et.al.(2020) the experience of loneliness among young people with depression : a qualitative meta synthesis of the literature. Result these themes illustrated range of pathways between depression and loneliness, and a sense of how these might be mutually reinforcing. our finding suggest that where depressed individual engage in cretin behaviors for a range of reason, this can lead to feeling of loneliness, an awareness, of which worsens their mood, thus perpetuating their depression. Rawal,S.(2020). The relationship between anxiety and loneliness among college students a recent study indicated that anxiety levels have explained in recent year, particularly among youth adults. Students at the college appear more depressed and nervous than ever before. According to psychologist, loneliness can actually be a source of anxiety

Statement of the Problem:

A Study of Relationship between Loneliness and Mental Depression Among college Students.

Objectives:

- 1) To examine the relationship between Loneliness and Mental Depression among college Students.
- 2) To find the gender difference of Loneliness and Mental Depression of college Students.
- 3) To examine the effect of college student Loneliness on Mental Depression among them.

Hypotheses:

- 1) There is a Positive correlation of Loneliness and Mental Depression among college students.
- 2) There is significant gender difference Loneliness and Mental Depression among college students.
- 3) Loneliness would be significantly influence on Mental Depression among college students.

Sample:

A sample of 80 college students from Pune Hadpsar (Senior College). Age range between 20

to 21years.

Tools

Loneliness Inventory:

This inventory was constructed and developed by Uma, Meenakshi under the guidance of Krishnan(2008). There are only 19 statements in the inventory. With each statement author has provided five alternatives. They are never, rarely, sometimes, many a times, and always. Reliability coefficient was computed by using Spearman-Brown formula. Reliability coefficient for the inventory was 0.84.

Mental Depression Scale:

It was developed dubey(2006). Depression among the Ss was measured with the help of this scale. There are 50 statements in the scale. Each statement is associated with two alternatives YES and NO. The job of S is to read each statement carefully and then decide whether the statement is applicable to him or not. If it applies to him or her, he/she has to put a tick mark in the square denoting yes. If it does not then he/she has to put a tick mark in the square denoting No. All the 50 statements are framed in such a manner that yes reply means depression and No reply means no depression. Test-retest reliability reported by the author was 0.64 and split half reliability was 0.69. Validity coefficient was 0.41.

Procedure:

The researcher personally visited the college. It was explained to them that the information gathered would be used only for the research purpose & everything, including their identity, would be kept highly confidential. In this way better rapport it established & subjects usually give correct responses because they know they are being observed.

Result and Discussion:

The main purpose of the present study was investigating relationship between and gender difference loneliness and mental depression. And examine loneliness influence on mental depression for this purpose investigator formulated three hypotheses are shown in the tables.

Table 1: showing percentage of total Loneliness College Student.

students	N	Mean	Std. Dev	t value	Significant
Male	20	53.05	9.6	2.15	Significant at 0.05
Female	20	46.6	9.3		

Table 1: show that there is loneliness of the sample selected in the present investigation. Male Mean 53.05 and standard deviation 9.6 and female mean 46.6 and standard deviation 9.3. The calculated t value 2.15 is significant at 0.05 level.

Table 2 : showing percentage of total Mental Depression College student.

students	N	Mean	Std. Dev	t value	Significant
Male	20	22.8	2.9	2.11	Significant at 0.05
Female	20	24.7	2.8		

Table 2 : show that there is Mental Depression of the sample selected in the present investigation. Male Mean 22.8 and standard deviation 2.9 and female mean 24.7 and standard deviation 2.8. The calculated t value 2.11 is significant at 0.05 levels.

The obtained correlation coefficient between Loneliness and mental depression in the present investigation is -0.24 it is significant at 0.05 levels with 78 df. This indicates correlation of loneliness and mental depression.

Third hypothesis is not significant because sample was very small that reason loneliness not influence on mental depression.

Conclusions:

There is significant gender difference of Loneliness and mental depression.

There is significant correlation of loneliness and mental depression.

The Loneliness is not significantly influence on Mental Depression among college students.

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